

THE PROBLEM AND METHODS OF ENLARGING STUDENT VOCABULARY IN THE ENGLISH CLASSES AT NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES.

Kambarova L.R.

- Teacher

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN AND EXACT SCIENCES,
TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS, TASHKENT,
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Email: Li26ka0695@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

At present days, we can observe a transition from a communicative approach to teaching a language to its diversity - an interactive approach in the modern methodology of teaching foreign languages. Interactive methods are aimed at a wider interaction of students not only with the teacher, but also with each other, as well as at increasing the activity of students in the learning process.

The aim of the work is the confirmation of the efficiency of the application of interactive forms of learning in teaching a foreign language (English) in the nonlinguistic universities. For example, in some nonlinguistic universities where the major is economics or IT field, students do not need to go deep into the whole grammar of the English language, for them a superficial knowledge of English will go. Since they work with IT technologies or study the system of economics, it is advisable to study English, which is mainly associated with technology or related subject. To do this, they basically need to know the meanings of foreign words regarding their qualification. Therefore, emphasis should be placed on enriching vocabulary. To do this, it is better to conduct lessons in such classes in an interactive form.

Interactive learning (direct translation of the term "interactive" interacting) is a modern way of learning, which consists in the interaction of all participants in the educational process: teachers and students. Today, this method of teaching is widely used everywhere: in schools, universities, courses and trainings, because this technique is extremely effective not only in terms of gaining knowledge, but also in

terms of the formation of personal skills and the development of the character of students.

Teaching foreign languages at a university using interactive methods is aimed at solving a number of problems: enriching vocabulary for students; communicative and cognitive, which teaches communication skills; specifically, cognitive, which takes into account the

specific educational situation; socially oriented, which forms and develops an adequate socialization of a person outside the educational situation.

It is important that interactive teaching methods can be applied to almost all types of training: in personal meetings, in groups, on the Internet, by telephone.

During the interactive lesson, the teacher and students are in equal conditions, at the same level. In such lessons, the teacher does not teach material, but becomes an active participant in the discussion, directs it in the right direction. Any interactive lessons are useful for a person, because they are taught to express their opinions and defend their point of view.

Interactive methods of teaching English help students not only exchange information, but also gain practical communication skills in the language they are studying, learn to formulate their thoughts, quickly respond and respond to replicas of the interlocutor. In such lessons, the teacher is no longer just a leader, but an assistant who can quickly tell the right word, correct a mistake. Interactive methods of teaching English can help facilitate the teaching\learning process.

Technologies of interactive learning can be classified as following:

- 1) passive - the student acts as the "object a" of learning (listens and looks)
 - 2) active - the student acts as the "subject" of training (independent work, creative tasks)
 - 3) interactive - inter (mutual), act (act).
- The learning process is conducted in the conditions of constant, active interaction of all students. The student and teacher are regarded as equal subjects of instruction.

The implementation of an interactive learning model contributes to for the

modeling of life situations, including role-playing activities, problem solving. Besides, there is no the dominance of any participant in the learning process. This teaches a humane, democratic approach to the model.

There are following examples of Interactive Learning Technologies:

1. Work in pairs.
2. Rotational (replaceable) triples.
3. Work in small groups.
4. Incomplete offer.
5. Brainstorming.
6. Brownian motion.
7. The court on its own behalf.
8. Civil hearings.
9. Role-playing (business) game.
10. Press method.
11. Discussion.
12. Debate.

Many of the main methodological innovations associated today with the use of interactive teaching methods. Interactive learning is, first of all, interactive learning, in the course of which the teacher and student interact.

What are the main features of the "interactive"? It should be recognized that interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity. She has in mind very specific and predictable goals. One of these goals is to create a comfortable learning environment, such that the student feels his success, his intellectual viability, which makes the learning process productive.

Interactive activity in the lessons involves the organization and development of dialogue communication, which leads to mutual understanding, interaction, to joint solution of common, but significant for each participant tasks. During the interactive training, students learn to think

critically, solve complex problems based on an analysis of circumstances and relevant information, weigh alternative opinions, make informed decisions, participate in discussions, and communicate with other people. For this, individual, group and group work is organized in the lessons, research projects, role-playing games are applied, work is underway with documents and various sources of information, and creative work is used.

Stages of Interactive Learning Technology

The following stages can be distinguished in the structure of the learning process using ILT:

1. Orientation.
2. Preparation for
3. Discussion.

The use of ILT allows the teacher to combine the activities of each student (a whole system of interactions arises: teacher - student, teacher - class, student - class, student - student, group - group), to connect his educational activities and interpersonal cognitive communication.

Engaging students in interactive activities in English classes

The basis of modern innovative technologies is personality-oriented training. In the practice of teaching a foreign language, a number of personality-oriented technologies can be applied. Interactive learning technology is one of them. The technology of learning in interaction is based on the use of various methodological strategies and techniques for modeling situations of real communication and the organization of interaction of students in a group (in pairs, in small groups) in order to jointly solve communicative problems.

The use of interactive forms of the lesson enriches not only the student, but also the teacher, expands his methodological tools, stimulates search, initiative, and makes him keep up to date. The purpose of using the interactive teaching method is to form a motivated interest in the English language, to create conditions for the development of students' speech competence in various types of speech activity, which leads to mutual understanding, interaction, and joint solution of common issues. The task is to make each lesson interesting, exciting and to ensure that it develops cognitive interest, encourages students to actively participate in the educational process.

The following types of interactive lessons are acceptable for foreign language lessons:

1. Lesson - role-playing game
2. Lesson consultation
3. Art lessons
4. Lesson - auction
1. Lesson - offset
2. Lessons of doubt
3. Lesson - Competition (quiz)
4. Lesson and fantasies
5. Lesson game
6. Lesson - tour
7. Lesson Collage

Information and communication technologies in teaching English in an interactive lesson

The trends of globalization, global integration in various fields of economic, technical, cultural, social and individual life place high demands on the practical knowledge of the English language. In the context of a change in the content of education, when there is a transition from a knowledge-centric approach to competency, information and communication technologies play a priority

role in the educational process. The use of information and communication technologies reveals the enormous potential of a computer as a learning tool. Computer-based training programs have many advantages over traditional teaching methods.

They allow you to train different types of speech activities and combine them in different combinations, help to understand linguistic phenomena, form linguistic abilities, create communicative situations, automate language and speech actions, and also provide the ability to take into account the leading representative system, implement an individual approach and intensify students' independent work.

The computer is considered as a tool to increase motivation, the formation of strong language skills and improve English proficiency. The computer allows the student to use all three channels of perception: auditory, visual and kinesthetic, which allows to increase the volume and strength of assimilation of the material studied, significantly increases the status of students in the educational process, increases the cognitive activity of students and maintains interest in the subject. In multimedia educational programs in English, various methodological techniques are used, which allow for familiarization, training and control of students' knowledge and skills. The use of multimedia programs does not at all preclude traditional teaching methods, but is harmoniously combined with them at all stages of training.

Listening to broadcast programs develops students' listening skills, while deepening their knowledge of the subject.

Possible types of work in programs: Microsoft Word, Microsoft Excel, Power

Point, recording slides, presentations, using a multimedia projector and electronic interactive whiteboard, searching the Internet.

Using Internet Resources

The computer and the Internet provide invaluable assistance to the teacher in preparing and conducting lessons on regional geography. Access to the Internet has virtually eliminated the problem of the lack of authentic multimedia resources necessary for the preparation and conduct of interesting and effective classes that take into account current trends in the development of the English language, regional geographic realities and the requirements for educational material in the context of the new educational content.

The information obtained on the Internet can be used by the teacher both for preparing the lesson, and as illustrative and educational material in the lessons. The Internet creates a virtual sociocultural and linguistic environment by providing communication programs (chat rooms, mail, etc.), makes it possible to virtually visit a particular country, and provides the opportunity to participate in various projects, including foreign ones.

ICT design work

A computer can also be used in group work on a project where students with different levels of computer literacy are united, and the work is organized so that everyone can improve their existing skills and master new operations. The project method is based on the development of cognitive, creative skills of project participants.

In order to make the lesson as informational and visual as possible, the teacher absolutely needs knowledge of at least the basic application programs. Using

Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Word applications, students can be reflected.

The Microsoft Word program can be used for exercises on the correct spelling of learned words, building sentences, transforming sentences, issuing a theory and performing training exercises.

Microsoft Power Point program - using the tools of this program you can create good simulators for introducing new vocabulary and grammar. For example: a presentation (vocabulary and / or grammar) + a series of exercises (with control correctly - wrong) + scoring + to an on-test test or exercise.

Microsoft Excel program - using the tools of this program you can also create similar exercises with summing up the results of testing, the number of errors made, and returning to incorrectly executed offers.

The use of ICT allows you to create visual aids with minimal time and as a result to increase the visualization and fascination of the lesson, visualize the lesson using multimedia elements, which, unlike posters, can be adjusted as necessary. Equally important is the fact that such visual aids are stored in electronic form and do not require a lot of space in laboratory rooms. In addition, the lesson can be held not only in a specially equipped class, but also in any other room where you can expand the screen and video projection equipment with a computer (laptop).

Forms of work with ICT:

1. frontal;
2. group;
3. steam room;
4. individual.

Tasks can be used in a lesson in a regular classroom with a computer and a projector for conducting a frontal survey, when students alternately perform tasks at the

computer, and the class monitors what is happening on the screen. It was noted that when using this form of training, all students, regardless of the level of preparation and degree of activity in ordinary lessons, tried to get to the computer to enter their answer from the keyboard. An unusual attention was also paid to the answer of the comrade: the whole class turned into a single whole, following the student's response, which indicates an increase in motivation to study the subject.

In the study of foreign languages, ICT is most successfully used for:

- the formation of new knowledge;
- putting knowledge into practice.

Discussion of material covered (conversational practice).

Conclusion

An interactive lesson is an important educational lesson that has an unconventional structure. It is easy to notice that some types of classes were included in the category of interactive lessons, which in the previous classifications appeared as auxiliary, extracurricular, and extracurricular forms of organization of educational work, and their names give some idea of the goals, objectives, and methods of conducting such classes. It must be concluded that students in the interactive lessons are diligent and diligent. They do not have to be bored. Finally, the marks that the children receive for the lesson are much higher than those they receive in traditional lessons. Interactive teaching methods are a special form of organizing cognitive and communicative activities in which students find themselves involved in the cognitive process, have the ability to understand and reflect on what they know and think.

Teacher's place in interactive lessons often comes down to directing students to achieve lesson goals. He develops a lesson plan (as a rule, this is a set of interactive exercises and assignments, during which a student studies the material).

Thus, the main components of interactive lessons are interactive exercises and assignments that are performed by students. The fundamental difference between interactive exercises and tasks from ordinary ones is that in the course of their implementation not only material already learned is fixed, but also new material is studied. Interactive exercises and exercises are designed for the so-called interactive approaches.

1. Creative approach.

Creative work enables students not only to study the topic more deeply, but also significantly broadens their general horizons, teaches communication, the ability to independently obtain and select the necessary material, and makes it possible to develop not only collective creativity, but also individual talents and abilities of students.

2. Work in small groups

When a student works in a group, he contributes to the solution of the communicative problem, he is involved in activities.

Appealing a statement by Confucius: "Tell me - and I will forget; show me - maybe I will remember; involve me - and I will understand," I conclude that an interactive lesson is the best experience of active cooperation between a teacher and a student. Particularly noteworthy is the positive emotional mood of the students not only towards each other, but also towards the lesson as a whole, as well as their increased activity, desire to expand their horizons, and acquire new knowledge on the topic under study. This confirms the effectiveness of the interactive learning method.

When activating, consolidating one or another lexical, grammatical material, a very interesting form of work is the online lessons, where students can learn their level of knowledge by performing an entrance test. With the use of computer technology, students can find out your level of English language.

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